

Ethics Review Process Guidelines on Amendments

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1 Guidelines on when and how to submit an Amendment to an ethics application

This document provides detailed guidance on when to submit amendments, ensuring that your study remains (i) *ethically sound* and (ii) *compliant with institutional requirements*. At the end of the document, you can also find a list of the frequently asked questions, including instructions on how to submit an amendment. If you have any doubts or require assistance, please consult the ethics secretary (contacts provided below) – and, if necessary, the Data Steward and Privacy Officer – of your faculty.

1.1 What is an amendment and when you need to amend your application

An ‘amendment’ refers to any **modification** (changes and/or additions, also referred to as ‘addendum’) made to a previously approved ethics application. Often, these changes need to be reported to and re-approved by the ethics committee because they could impact the study's **ethical considerations**.

What do we mean by ‘ethical considerations’ in these guidelines?

Good to know: If you are unfamiliar with what changes qualify as an “ethical consideration”, this snapshot will help you get started.

An **ethical consideration** refers to any aspect of a study that potentially impacts the rights and well-being of participants (including researchers), as well as the integrity of the research itself. When making changes to a study (i.e., ‘amendment’), it is important to consider whether these introduce **new ethical considerations**. Research ethics evaluates each study on its own merits and individually, so there is no strict, standard definition of an “amendment.” However, some modifications raise (more or less obvious) ethical concerns that typically require committee review because **they affect core elements of ethical research**, such as participant safety or the integrity of consent processes. Common examples of these cases are:

- Changes that could increase risks for participants and/or researchers
- Modifications to the informed consent process
- Increased burden on participants (e.g., additional time or effort)
- Adjustments that impact power dynamics
- Potential conflicts of interest
- Any other modifications that may be ethically relevant

2 Requirements per topic

To facilitate the navigation of the document, the major topics that most frequently require the amendment of the ethics application in case of modification have been grouped in broad thematic areas.

- Participation in research.
- Materials, measurements, questionnaires and datasets.
- Methodology.
- Information, Consent, Deception/Debriefing procedure.
- Practical information.

2.1 Changes to participation in research

Introduction of a new group of participants	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<p>a) If the new group of participants require a different:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recruitment procedure. • Information letter. • Consent Form. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the group is very similar to the group of participants described in the approved application and recruitment and data collection procedures remain unaltered. • Any modification to the group of participants that does not alter any other aspect of the application.
<p>b) If the group of participants includes individual(s) who may be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Vulnerable. • In a subordinate or dependent relation to the researcher(s). 	
<p>Actionable suggestions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Has the study been modified to include an additional or different participant group, or have the changes affected the demographics of the research population? Describe accurately the new group of participants in the amended application. • Could the new group of participants, or individuals in the group, be considered vulnerable? Describe how this vulnerability will be accounted for throughout the project (recruitment, data collection, after care, etc.). • Does the new group of participants require a different recruitment procedure (incl. briefing, consent etc.)? See 2.4. below. • Could the new group of participants be in a relationship of dependency with the researcher(s)? Describe how this will be dealt with, as well as any adverse effects of this relationship. • Include new or updated documentation, such as information letters and/or consent forms. The DMP also should be updated accordingly, especially in case of (new) vulnerable groups. 	
Number of participants	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If a significant change (increase or decrease) is made in the number of participants requiring a revision of (other parts of) the ethics application (e.g., fairness in recruitment, modifications on Informed Consent, safety of participants and confidentiality measures, compensation, etc.). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the increase, or decrease, of the number of participants is not major and does not influence other parts of the ethics application.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Please contact the <u>ethics secretary of your faculty</u> 	
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide the old and new number of participants. Explain why you will be recruiting more or fewer participants. Consider whether this change might compromise the anonymity of participants and change information letters and/or consent forms accordingly. Any changes in anonymization measures should also be reflected in the DMP. 	
Recruitment Procedure	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the changes contradict what previously stated in the informed consent. If the changes to the recruitment procedure affect the data collection method (interviews, surveys, focus groups, experiments; refer also to 2.3 below). If the safety of participants and/or researchers may be compromised due to the changes. If privacy concerns arise with the changes (e.g., collection of sensitive data). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If the changes in the recruitment procedure are not significant and do not affect any other section of the application.
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe how the recruitment procedure has changed and any consequences. If additional sensitive personal data needs to be collected, describe how this will be processed (collected, stored, archived, deleted). Include updated documentation such as information letters and/or consent forms. 	
Compensation for participants	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In all instances 	/
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Describe what kind of compensation (including incentives and reimbursements) is provided and whether this is higher or lower than previously planned. Describe to which participants you will provide the compensation, if it is not provided to everyone. Describe why the new compensation is deemed relevant and reasonable. Include updated documentation such as information letters and/or consent forms. 	

2.2 Changes to Materials, Measurements, Questionnaires, Datasets

New questionnaires	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addition of questions and/or questionnaires dealing with a theme that was not included in the original application. • Addition of questions and/or questionnaires dealing with a sensitive or invasive topic, even if this topic was already included in the original application. • Addition of questions and/or questionnaires asking for sensitive (personal) information of the participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire(s) are removed. • New questions on a (non-sensitive) topic that was already described in the original application. • Approval was obtained for an open/exploratory design.
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe and include the new questions/questionnaire. • Indicate whether sensitive data will be collected with the new questionnaire. Collecting (personal) sensitive data, including sensitive questions or changes in the duration of the study, might require changes to the information letter or consent form. Include new documents if pertinent. • Indicate whether the burden of participating might increase. This can include longer duration of participation, or measures or questions that can be considered invasive or sensitive. If the burden of participation may be increased, describe how the additional burden on participants will be dealt with. • Could the addition lead to incidental findings? If so, describe what these could be and how you will deal with them. 	
New existing Dataset	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the new dataset contains identifiable data. • If the new dataset will be combined with other dataset(s) triggering potential privacy risks. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset does not contain personal data (fully anonymous).
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the dataset (this could be either your own dataset, data collected by another researcher or data collected and owned by a third party) and address potential privacy concerns (e.g., identifiable data, risk of identification due to linking). • Indicate whether permission for the use of the dataset for research purposes is required (from the owner of the data or individuals whose data is included) and upload proof of such permission. 	
New wave/round of Data Collection	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the new wave/round introduces changes such as those described in 2.1. and 2.2. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the new wave and/or round of data collection is identical to previous phases of the research.
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the new wave/round of data collection and explain how it is different from that part of the project that was previously approved by the ethics committee. • Indicate whether the same participants will be asked to participate in the new wave/round of data collection. If so, indicate whether participants were previously informed about the new wave/round of data collection. • Describe how participants will be asked to (re)confirm consent. • Consider which other parts of these guidelines apply. 	
Introducing or dismissing a Gatekeeper	
Amendments required	Amendments not required

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there are substantial changes in the role of the gatekeeper, such as the inclusion of a new individual (or entity) responsible for granting access to participants or data. • If the consent procedure changes, such as when formal permission becomes necessary to access non-public domain data, or if there are updates to the consent documents. • If the research setting shifts from public to private locations, making formal permission necessary, or if fieldwork identifies key individuals necessary to the research. • If the role of the gatekeeper becomes irrelevant and is no longer necessary for the study. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the gatekeeper is a different person but plays a similar function in the research setting, and both the consent procedure and project design remain unchanged (unless change has impact on other aspects of the application).
<p>Actionable suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Is a gatekeeper needed to access a certain group of participants/study setting, or is a new gatekeeper required due to their better suitability for the research context compared to the original plan, or is it no longer necessary to have a gatekeeper? Describe the role of the new gatekeeper and explain the reasons behind the changes. • Consider and, if pertinent, describe vulnerability of participants to gatekeeper (e.g., in case of relation of dependency with gatekeeper). • Identify concerns in terms power relations and the diversity of interests at play (e.g., does the gatekeeper represent the community? Can they withhold access from the community? How does that relate to the interests of the research and your position as researchers?). • If applicable, describe how the recruitment procedure changes and include new or updated information letter(s) and/or consent forms (e.g., formal institutions that need to accord permission to obtain key documents or people under their care). 	

2.3 Methodology

New procedure and/or significant alteration to procedure	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All instances 	/
<p>Actionable suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe all the modifications and procedures accurately, as they may bear ethical considerations, and pay special attention to the following areas: • Addition of a new procedure. • Introduction of another data collection method (e.g., interviews, surveys, focus groups, experiments). • Significant increase or decrease in the burden on participants (e.g., number of sessions to attend). • Alteration of the chosen medium (e.g., shifting from paper to digital, from audio to video). • Describe what will be expected of participants during this addition to the study. • Describe and upload new materials (measurements or questionnaires) that are used (see 2.) • Pay particular attention to any risks or burden to participants this may entail and how the information/consent procedure needs to be amended. • Include updated DMP, as well as updated or new information letters and/or consent forms. • Consider which other parts of these guidelines apply. 	

<p>✓ For ERIM committees only: If your study changes from experimental to non-experimental (or vice versa), you must submit a new application to the appropriate committee. If you are unsure, please contact the ERIM ethics advisor.</p>	
Location	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the new location may impose an increased burden on participants (e.g., new location requires participants to travel further, increasing time and effort). • If the new location may increase traceability of participants (e.g., new location is a small community setting where participants' identities might be easily recognized by others). • If the new location may impose a risk on participants and/or the researcher (e.g., an area with political instability or unsafe conditions). • If there are specific social or cultural norms at the new location that need to be taken into consideration. • If the new location is in a low or lower-middle income country (if these were not included previously). • If the new location is outside of the EU (if these were not included previously). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there is no practical change for the participant. • If the new location is comparable to the previously selected location(s). • If the new location decreases burden for participants.
<p>Actionable suggestions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the new location and why the changes were necessary. • Consider if the location may impose a burden on participants and/or whether it may impose a risk, if and how the conditions of the new location might increase the traceability of participants and if the new location may impose a risk on researchers involved. If so, discuss mitigation strategies. • Include any new or updated information letters and/or consent forms, as well as information about age of consent in non-EU countries. Make sure the information sheet and consent form is updated accordingly. It should also be compliant with the laws of the country in which the data is collected. • Include any information about benefit-sharing, in case low or lower-middle income countries are added. 	

2.4 Information, Consent, Deception/Debriefing procedure

Revisions to the terms outlined in the Informed Consent Form	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If substantive changes are made to the documents used to obtain their consent (or assent) to participate in the study. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the documents/information presented to participants are translated to another language than the document approved by the committee. • If text or language is simplified without loss of content or meaning. • If corrections are applied to spellings, typos or data that were inaccurately recorded or reported.
<p>Actionable suggestions:</p>	

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report any changes to the language or content used to inform participants and secure their consent/assent (including adjustments to the information letter, consent form, debriefing details and other materials). Changes should be clearly indicated. • Consult the EUR Informed Consent templates for advice on content and structure. • Upload any amended documents. 	
Changes to consent procedure outlined in the Informed Consent form	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In all instances. 	/
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the changes include switching from written to oral consent (or vice versa), from active to passive consent (or vice versa) or using a new medium (e.g., text > video)? Describe thoroughly the changes to the consent/assent procedure and explain why the changes are necessary. • Include updated documentation such as information letters and/or consent forms or provide the information text when using alternatives to written consent. 	
Withholding information or using Deception	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If withholding information or using deception are introduced to the study. • If the nature of the information which is being withheld from participants is changed. • If changes are made to the timing of the debriefing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If changes consist of minor revisions to an already approved form of deception and/or withholding of information, especially if the changes reduce the amount of information withheld and/or clarify communication.
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Explain why the changes are necessary. • Describe what information is being withheld from participants and explain why this is necessary. • Describe if and how participants will be fully informed after the study (debriefing), and if not, explain why not. • Include the debriefing form and other amended documents. 	

2.5 Practical information

Research Team	
Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If any conflicts of interest may arise when new staff members who are directly involved in the study (e.g., for data collection) are added to the project. • If the principal investigator (PI) or the lead researcher responsible for the study changes. • If external collaborators (both academic institutions and non-academic parties) not originally included in the application are added. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If minor changes within the team occur without influencing the project design, ethical considerations or methodology.
Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Before submitting the amendment, please contact the ethics secretary of your faculty to discuss possible ethical implications if the research involves privacy concerns and/or sensitive information. 	

- Are any members added to or removed from the research team who are directly involved in participant interactions? Explain how the duties that involve handling sensitive participant data or direct communication with participants will be reassigned.
- Update the application by listing the names and roles of any new team members and contact the Ethics Secretary of your faculty to grant the new team member access to the application, if necessary.
- Any information sheet and Informed Consent forms should also be updated accordingly.
- Include details about the new external collaborators, describe their role in the project and explain how their involvement will benefit the study.
- If pertinent, describe how any potential or perceived conflicts of interest are handled.
- Update the DMP to reflect the pertinent changes.

Changes in Research Timeline

Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the study timeline is significantly extended or reduced. • If any changes in the timeline impact (negatively) the length or the nature of participant involvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If changes to timeline do not impact the project design significantly. • If participant recruitment is slightly delayed but does not impact the participants' wellbeing and remuneration. • If adjustments to internal project deadlines do not affect the timeline for participant interactions.

Actionable suggestions:

- Is the timeline of your research changing significantly? Is this also impacting the research group participating in the study (e.g., posing further risks or burden)? Explain the changes to the study timeline and how the new timeline changes may affect participants. If the changes increase risks or burdens, explain how these will be managed and minimized.
- If the extension or reduction impacts participants' involvement and/or consent, or their ability to withdraw, explain any steps taken to mitigate potential issues.
- Include updated documentation such as information letters and/or consent forms.

Changes to anonymized/pseudonymized data

Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In all instances 	/

Actionable suggestions:

- Do the changes impact the level of confidentiality promised to participants or do you plan to use (sensitive) personal data for purposes not covered in the original application? Explain why the changes are necessary and how these changes will impact participant confidentiality. If the new data management practices increase risks, outline the steps taken to mitigate these risks.
- Are you switching from anonymized to pseudonymized data or vice versa? Before submitting the amendment, you are strongly advised to consult with the Privacy Officer and/or the Data Steward of your faculty (if the changes also impact the way you will handle and store the data).
- Submit all relevant documents, such as revised data management plans, updated consent forms and any new data protection agreements.

Changes to personal data storage conflicting with Informed Consent form

Amendments required	Amendments not required
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If there are changes in data storage location and the new location is not listed among the EUR approved storage solutions. • If there are changes in data security measures (e.g., different encryption methods or access control protocols). • If you plan to store the data longer than originally planned. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • If the changes consist of minor updates to security protocols without affecting access control. • If you want to reorganize the data files without changing location/accessibility. • If minor changes occur to existing storage methods without compromising any sensitive information.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none">• If you want to share the data with third parties (e.g., new collaborations). | |
| Actionable suggestions: <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Before making changes, consult with the Privacy Officer to ensure compliance with data protection standards, and with the Data Stewards to ensure that the new storage solutions comply with EUR regulations.• Describe what and why changes are expected or being made, and how they impact data security and participant privacy.• If necessary, explain how you will inform participants of the changes and update any consent forms. | |

3 Contacts

The Ethics Secretary of your School is available for questions you may have concerning the amendments to your already approved ethics applications that you want to submit.

General email	ethics@eur.nl
ESSB-DPECS	ec-dpecs@essb.eur.nl
ESSB-DPAS	dpas-ethics@essb.eur.nl
ESL	ethicsreview@law.eur.nl
ESHCC	ethicsreview@eshcc.eur.nl
ESHPM	research.reviewboard@eshpm.eur.nl
ISS	researchethics@iss.nl
ESPhil	ethicsreview@esphil.eur.nl
ERIM (RSM and ESE)	erim-re@erim.eur.nl
IHS	ethics@ihs.nl

4 FAQs

4.1 At what point should I submit an amendment?

You should notify the ethics committee about any modifications or changes to your ethics application in a **timely manner**, especially when they involve a new wave / round of data collection or impact participants. Please note that if new data collection is involved, it is crucial to obtain ethics approval for your amendments *before* beginning the collection. Retrospective evaluations are, as a general rule, not accepted by ethics committees (exceptions may apply; consult with your faculty's ethics secretary).

4.2 How do I submit an amendment?

To submit an amendment, use the [Ethics Monitor](#) platform. Open your approved application, and choose one of the following options on the right side of the screen:

Submit an Amendment

The system will prompt you to describe the amendments and upload any relevant documents. The amendment will be assigned a new unique identifier but will remain linked to the original application in the system. Once the amendments are approved, you will receive a new approval letter for your records, specifying that the changes to the original application have been approved

Copy of a similar application

If the amendments to your application affect multiple areas of the study (or multiple questions in the application form), you may also choose to create a "Copy" of your previously approved application. This option provides access to the full already filled in ethics questionnaire which you can modify according to your needs. This will allow the committee to see the changes made to the original application. The new application will automatically be linked to the original one. When using this function, your new application will be assigned a new unique identifier and once approved and you will receive a new letter of approval referring to the copy only (i.e., the letter of approval of a copied application does not mention the original application). Please note that only one copy for each application can be created. For more details, please refer to the Ethics Monitor manual for applicants [here](#).

4.3 How will my amended application be reviewed?

Each ethics committee has its own regulations for evaluating applications and amendments. Generally, once you submit an amendment, the ethics secretary will process it and determine the appropriate review process based on the nature of the changes. For instance, minor or formal modifications may be reviewed by one member of the ethics committee, while significant changes involving new data collection or that have an impact on participants may require a full review (including, if necessary, the Privacy Officer and the Data Steward of your faculty). The review timeframe varies depending on the committee's regulations and the scope of the amendment. To avoid delays, it is strongly recommended to submit your amendment in due time, along with all relevant documentation, and (if needed) to consult with the Privacy Officer and the Data Steward of your faculty prior submission.

4.4 When should a new application be submitted?

You should submit a new application when significant changes to the project design alter multiple or key aspects of the original application, or new research components are introduced. In such cases, a new application that accurately reflects the updated study is necessary. If you have doubts, please contact the [ethics secretary of your faculty](#). For more details, please see above ('How do I submit an amendment') and refer to the Ethics Monitor manual for applicants [here](#).